

Distributed System of Scientific Collections RI

Service Provision

General Framework Agreement

Document Version Control

Version	Description	Author(s)
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0.2	Adjustments following 1st SP meeting	D. Koureas
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0. Purpose of the DiSSCo Service Provision General Framework Agreement (SP/GFA)

The DiSSCo Service Provision General Framework Agreement (SP/GFA) establishes the basic rules and general terms governing future Service Provision agreements between the DiSSCo ERIC and National Nodes and/or Institutions that will act as DiSSCo Service Providers. Notably, the SP/GFA sets out baseline expectations and addresses general topics linked to the specific terms of DiSSCo Service Provision agreements. The SP/GFA is not a commercial procurement framework. Its general principles, however, may also apply to commercial contractors or subcontractors.

This SP/GFA does not apply to or regulate the provision of collections-derived data by DiSSCo facilities to the DiSSCo RI. All DiSSCo facilities are expected to provide collections-derived data to DiSSCo RI to the best of their capacity. As such, no contractual agreements will be in place to govern the sharing of data by DiSSCo facilities with DiSSCo ERIC.

All future Specific Service Provision Agreements must be drafted in accordance with this SP/GFA and comply with its terms.

1. Definition of a DiSSCo Services and Service Provider

Definition of DiSSCo Service

A DiSSCo Service refers to activities, resources, or capabilities provided by a DiSSCo Service Provider that supports the mission, objectives, and operations of the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure (RI). Services may include digital resources, physical access, virtual access, training, capacity building, community support, and other related activities.

DiSSCo services must be included in the Service Providers' Service Delivery Plan and governed by a Service Level Agreement between the Service Provider and DiSSCo ERIC.

The DiSSCo ERIC compiles a catalogue of DiSSCo Services and updates it regularly according to the needs of the DiSSCo RI scientific programme.

Who can offer a DiSSCo Service

DiSSCo Services are offered by DiSSCo Service Providers on behalf of the DiSSCo ERIC. Service Providers operate under agreements with DiSSCo ERIC to deliver specific services that support the DiSSCo RI's objectives. Entities not affiliated with DiSSCo (i.e. not part of the DiSSCo RI) may also offer services contracted out by a National Node on behalf of the DiSSCo RI or by DiSSCo ERIC.

Definition of a DiSSCo Service Provider

A Service Provider is an organisation or institution, typically a National Node or an entity part of or endorsed by a National Node, that offers one or more DiSSCo Services through a Service Level Agreement (SLA) with DiSSCo ERIC. SLAs define the exact nature of each service and outline the responsibilities of Service Providers and DiSSCo ERIC, ensuring the delivery of high-quality services in alignment with DiSSCo's objectives.

2. Definition of terms

Service Level Agreement (SLA)

A contractual agreement between the service provider and DiSSCo ERIC outlines the expected service level to be provided. It defines specific, measurable standards for the service's quality, availability, and responsibilities, such as response times, resolution times, performance benchmarks, and customer support.

Key elements of an SLA include:

- Description of services provided
- Performance standards and metrics (e.g., uptime, response time, content accuracy, update frequency, user feedback)
- Roles and responsibilities of both parties
- Monitoring and reporting procedures
- Remedies for non-compliance, e.g. unforeseen events

Service Delivery Plan (SDP)

The Service Delivery Plan is a detailed document that focuses on the practical aspects of delivering a service. It ensures that clear processes, resources, and timelines are in place to achieve service goals and meet the needs and expectations of DiSSCo stakeholders. It describes what services will be provided, how they will be delivered, when, by whom, and to what standard. It is an operational document and not a contractual agreement.

While an SLA sets the expectations and standards for service performance, a Service Delivery Plan explains how those services will be practically delivered to meet those standards.

Key elements of a SDP include:

- Description of services and objectives
- Target audience
- Roles and responsibilities of staff
- Processes and procedures for delivering services
- Resources required (people, equipment, budget)
- Quality standards
- Risk management and contingency plans
- Timelines and schedules

Data Processing Agreement (DPA)

A DPA is a legally binding contract between a data controller and a data processor that governs how personal data is handled, processed, and protected. It is required under laws like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) when a third party (the processor) processes personal data on behalf of an organisation (the controller).

A DPA is only needed for services that handle personal data and ensure that personal data is processed lawfully, securely, and in accordance with data protection regulations.

Service Provision agreements

A general term for the agreements described above.

3. Benefits of becoming a DiSSCo Service Provider

By becoming a DiSSCo service provider, institutions position themselves as leaders in natural sciences, gaining tangible and strategic benefits while contributing to a pan-European research infrastructure. For example, being a service provider may help get involved in an EU-funded DiSSCo-related project, get in-kind contribution recognition, influence how biodiversity data standards are implemented in DiSSCo, and build capacity in the institution by learning the latest digitisation technologies and methodologies.

Summary of benefits

Benefit area	Examples of gains
Visibility & reputation	International recognition, citation, enhanced profile
Collaborations & networking	Partnerships, joint projects, research collaborations
Funding opportunities	Access to grants, shared resources, reduced individual costs
Strategic influence	Input to standards, services, governance
Improved data quality	Better data interoperability, wider use of collections
Capacity building	Staff training, shared expertise, technical support
Scientific & societal impact	Contribution to research, policy, and public understanding

4. National Nodes responsibilities towards DiSSCo RI

National Nodes are responsible for identifying and building on the strengths of the national science community and their needs. They can provide services to build on these strengths or resources to enable DiSSCo service providers in their country.

National Nodes:

- Shall engage and facilitate existing and new DiSSCo service providers in their country;

- Provide or coordinate the necessary capacity building for service providers and coordinate between national service providers and DiSSCo ERIC for communication, regular monitoring of service provider agreements and providing information about service providers;
- Shall monitor the status of policy self-assessments of national service providers to report on alignment with the policies implemented in the DiSSCo RI;
- May advise DiSSCo RI, through the Nodes Advisory Committee, on national priorities, trends, and user needs regarding DiSSCo services;
- May act on behalf of national facilities in signing SLAs with DiSSCo ERIC to provide DiSSCo Services.

5. Classification of DiSSCo Services

Types of Services

Type	Description	Example Service
e-Services	Digital resources and tools that facilitate virtual access, research and collaboration	Digital Specimen Repository, ELViS System, DiSSCo Knowledge Base
Physical Resources	Facilitation of physical access to national collections and research facilities	On-site visits to institutional facilities or preparation and management of specimen loans
Data (on-demand) & Knowledge services	On-demand digitisation of natural science collections or on-demand execution of laboratory or field work or taxonomic identification	Provision of collection-derived data to DiSSCo, Project-based digitisation of collections and provision of extracted data
Training & Capacity building	Educational programs and resources that enhance the skills and knowledge of users	Workshops, online courses, development of training material
Engagement / Communication & Dissemination	Activities that promote awareness and utilisation of DiSSCo resources	Outreach programs, conferences, thematic workshops
Community Support	Services that support the research community, including user support and resource sharing	Helpdesk

Core and non-core Services

Core Services

Core Services are fundamental to the operation and sustainability of the DiSSCo infrastructure and cannot be left unmaintained ("orphaned"). A failure to maintain Core Services would compromise the functionality and operational capacity of the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure (RI). If a designated service provider is unavailable or unable to deliver or maintain a Core Service, the responsibility for ensuring its provision shall rest with the DiSSCo ERIC Central Hub. The Central Hub may either directly assume the provision of the Core Service or engage a subcontractor to fulfil this obligation.

At the commencement of the DiSSCo ERIC, the following services are classified as Core Services:

- (a) ELViS (European Loans and Visits System),
- (b) Digital Specimen Repository,
- (c) DiSSCover Platform,
- (d) Collection Digitisation Dashboard,
- (e) Knowledge Base, and
- (f) Helpdesk.

The list of core Services can be adjusted according to the RI's needs. After consulting with the national nodes committee and representatives of the Service Providers, the DiSSCo executive board will approve changes to the list of core services.

Core Services must adhere to a set of protected characteristics specified in the ERIC's Technical and scientific description. These characteristics ensure that all Core Services comply with the DiSSCo ERIC's overarching scientific and technical roadmap. Such compliance is essential to maintaining the integrity, functionality, and alignment of Core Services with the strategic goals of the DiSSCo RI.

Non-core Services

Non-core services are supplementary and enhance the overall user experience. If one of such services is discontinued, DiSSCo RI can still fulfil its scientific mission, but together, these are also critical for the operation of DiSSCo RI. The list of non-core services may be adjusted based on demand, technological advancements, or strategic decisions by the DiSSCo ERIC. Examples of non-core services are species identification services, machine annotation services, a crowdsourcing platform, an online course, physical access to a collection, etc.

Sharing of Personal Data

For services that share or process personal data, a Data Processing Agreement (DPA) is required between the data processor and data controller. The data controller decides why and how personal data is collected, stored, used, and shared.

6. Evaluation and Selection Process

General Criteria for selection

The selection of DiSSCo Service Providers is based on their ability to deliver high-quality, reliable services that align with the mission and objectives of the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure (RI). These services may include highly technical e-services and non-technical offerings, such as training, outreach, and community support. Prospective Service Providers will be assessed against the following inclusive criteria:

1. **Expertise and Capability**

Applicants must demonstrate expertise relevant to the type of service proposed, whether technical, educational, or community-focused. This includes:

- For technical services: Infrastructure, adherence to technical standards, and relevant operational experience.
- For non-technical services: Proven success in areas such as education, stakeholder engagement, or knowledge dissemination.

2. **Sustainability and Capacity**

Providers must show they have the resources to sustain service delivery throughout the contract. This includes:

- Financial stability is evidenced through documentation such as financial statements or operational funding commitments.
- Administrative structures capable of managing service provision effectively.
- Personnel or teams dedicated to ensuring consistent service quality.

3. **Alignment with DiSSCo Objectives**

Services must align with and contribute to DiSSCo's mission and strategic aims.

Examples include:

- Enhancing scientific impact through robust technical services or innovative training programmes.
- Supporting open science and fostering collaboration within the scientific community.
- Advancing public engagement or capacity building in alignment with DiSSCo's outreach objectives.

4. **Alignment with DiSSCo Policies and Standards**

Services must align with DiSSCo policies and standards, for example:

- Data Policy
- Access Policy
- openDS data models

5. Impact and Value

Applicants must outline how their service will contribute value to the DiSSCo ecosystem through innovation, efficiency, or community impact. This includes:

- Proposed metrics for success, such as user engagement for training programmes or data availability for technical services.
- Evidence of past impact or value delivery in similar initiatives.

6. Flexibility and Adaptability

Providers should demonstrate their ability to respond to evolving needs, including:

- For technical services: Scalability and readiness to integrate new technologies.
- For non-technical services: Adaptability to emerging trends in education, engagement, or stakeholder requirements.

7. Quality Assurance and Monitoring

All services, regardless of type, must include mechanisms to ensure quality and reliability, including:

- For technical services: Performance metrics such as uptime and interoperability.
- For non-technical services: User feedback and satisfaction as key indicators of quality.

Application Process

Prospective Service Providers must submit a detailed Service Delivery Plan outlining their proposed services, capabilities, resources and plans for the sustainability of the services. DiSSCo ERIC provides templates and guidelines for the submission process.

Evaluation Process

The evaluation process involves multiple stages, including:

1. **Initial Review:** DiSSCo Hub reviews the submitted Service Delivery Plans to ensure they meet the minimum criteria.
2. **Technical Assessment:** The Scientific, Ethical and Technical Advisory Committee evaluates the technical aspects of the proposals. The DiSSCo executive board might decide to seek advice from other stakeholders and experts.
3. **Final Decision:** The DiSSCo ERIC General Assembly (GA) makes the final decision based on the recommendations of the DiSSCo executive board.

Note that depending on the services to provide, a Service Delivery Plan may or may not be specific on the services to be offered by the service provider. For example, the SDP may be about one core service or a more generic plan to provide training services or MAS services without detailing the specific services. This is needed to keep the process agile when there are many DiSSCo services. To ensure rapid decisions, these can be made by correspondence outside of the regular Advisory Committee and General Assembly meetings. Once a Service Delivery Plan has been approved, DiSSCo Hub will arrange and monitor SLAs for the services.

For the transition period of DiSSCo, when decisions on the allocation of a core service is required to ensure the future construction and operation, the interim General Assembly shall approve the allocation of services to Service Providers after receiving the advice of the DiSSCo CSO.

Support is available for new Service Providers to build capacity, including training and resource allocation.

7. Quality assurance and Governance

Instruments for compliance and monitoring

Service Providers are required to comply with established Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and undergo regular monitoring. Instruments for compliance include:

- **Service Level Agreements and Service Delivery Plans**
- **Quality Assurance Framework:** Ensures services meet DiSSCo's KPIs and quality standards.
- **Monitoring and Reporting:** Regular reporting on usage metrics, user satisfaction, and service quality.

Service quality and monitoring framework

Expanded Key Components of the Quality and Monitoring Framework

To ensure the consistent delivery of high-quality services, the quality and monitoring framework incorporates the following key components, designed to provide clear standards, accountability, and continuous improvement:

Uptime/Availability

- **Definition:** Ensuring that services are accessible to users with minimal interruptions or downtime.
- **Standards:**
 - Service Level Agreements (SLAs) will specify minimum uptime requirements (e.g., 99.5% availability).
 - Maintenance windows must be scheduled in advance and communicated clearly to users.
 - Unplanned downtime must be promptly addressed, with contingency plans to minimise disruption.
- **Monitoring:**
 - Automated monitoring tools will track service uptime, with alerts for anomalies or failures.

- Reports on service availability will be reviewed regularly to identify trends and potential improvements.

Quality KPIs

- **Definition:** Establishing measurable performance indicators to evaluate service quality and effectiveness.
- **Examples:**
 - Response times for user queries or support tickets.
 - Data accuracy and completeness for services involving digital or physical resources.
 - User satisfaction ratings collected through surveys or feedback forms.
- **Implementation:**
 - Each service will have a tailored set of KPIs aligned with its specific objectives and user expectations.
 - Regular reviews will assess KPIs, with adjustments made to address underperformance.

Reporting

- **Definition:** Regular submission of comprehensive reports on service usage, challenges, and improvements.
- **Requirements:**
 - Reports should include usage patterns, service performance, and user feedback metrics.
 - Incidents or disruptions must be documented with details on causes, resolution, and preventive measures.
 - Improvement initiatives undertaken or planned must be highlighted.
- **Frequency:**
 - Reports will be submitted periodically (e.g., quarterly or semi-annually), as agreed in the SLA.
- **Review Process:**
 - DiSSCo ERIC will review submitted reports to ensure compliance and identify opportunities for enhancement.

Open Data/Open Source

- **Definition:** Compliance with DiSSCo's policies on open data and source code to promote transparency and collaboration.
- **Guidelines:**
 - Data generated or used by services must be made openly available, adhering to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.
 - Software developed for DiSSCo services should be released under an open-source licence.

- **Monitoring:**
 - Compliance audits will verify adherence to open data and open source requirements.
 - Non-compliance issues must be addressed promptly, with corrective actions documented and implemented.

User Support

- **Definition:** Providing users with sufficient support to ensure smooth access to and utilisation of services.
- **Components:**
 - **Helpdesk Services:** A dedicated helpdesk will be established to assist users with technical and operational queries.
 - **Documentation:** Comprehensive and user-friendly manuals, FAQs, and guides will be provided for each service.
 - **Training and Resources:** Workshops or online training sessions will be offered to enhance user understanding and capability.
- **Metrics:**
 - Response times for resolving user queries and issues will be tracked and optimised.
 - User satisfaction surveys will gauge the effectiveness of support services.
- **Continuous Improvement:**
 - Feedback loops will be implemented to use user suggestions and complaints for ongoing

Service Protected characteristics

We must ensure services comply with the overall DiSSCo scientific and technical programme. Protected characteristics regarding data are described in the Data Management Plan (see Annex 1 of the Technical and Scientific description of the ERIC). Further protected characteristics are described in the T&S description of the ERIC in 5.2 and describe protected characteristics regarding:

- Flexibility in Implementation
- Compliance with Standards
- Openness to Innovation
- Quality Assurance
- Capacity for Change Management
- Dispute Resolution Mechanisms
- Reporting and Transparency
- Risk Management
- Sustainability Commitment

e-Services should support and promote the usage of Digital Specimens and PIDs. In particular, e-Services must be able to interoperate with the DiSSCo data infrastructure APIs and, if applicable, identity and access management services. For

collections-derived data, e-Services should comply with the DiSSCo FAIR Digital Objects architecture.

8. Estimation of Service provisioning cost and value

Estimating service provisioning cost and value is crucial to ensure sustainable, impactful, and efficient services that support the research community. The service provisioning cost refers to the total resources needed to design, implement, maintain, and operate a service.

DiSSCo Service Providers are required to commit to providing all the data DiSSCo needs to calculate the costs, which can be provided through a Service Delivery Plan. DiSSCo aims to use multiple methods to calculate cost and value: the Full Economic Cost method (see DiSSCo Cost Book, [add link]), Personnel Costs in case a service only requires personnel costs, and it may also apply an Added-value Formula using socio-economic impact indicators to calculate value, see MS5 from the DiSSCo Transition Project. The cost of collections-derived data provision is at the partner's expense and does not need to be included in a Service Delivery Plan.

9. Lapse of Service Provider Obligations

DiSSCo service providers must report to DiSSCo ERIC about temporary or brief failures in the service's operation. When included in the SLA, a lapse of obligations may have financial implications. Services may have an end-of-life and an End-of-Support Life, which needs to be communicated well in advance, in line with agreements set out in a Service Level Agreement. DiSSCo ERIC is not liable for service provision issues.

10. Joint Responsibility of Service Providers and DiSSCo ERIC

Both parties must work collaboratively to ensure the success of the service provision. This includes shared responsibilities in service development, quality assurance, and addressing any challenges during the service period.